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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

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FEATURES OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT IN CHILDREN WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF LONG-TERM EFFECTS OF PERINATAL LESIONS OF THE CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM

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ANNOTATION

Objective: To study the impact of the long-term effects of perinatal CNS lesions on the physical development of children suffering from bronchial asthma.

Materials and Methods: In the first stage, the study focused on the anamnestic and clinical-functional characteristics of bronchial asthma in children with long-term effects of perinatal lesions of the central nervous system. The analytical part of the study includes the results of a comprehensive examination of 103 children aged 5 to 7 years diagnosed with bronchial asthma. The main group consisted of 72 children (51 boys and 21 girls) with bronchial asthma and signs of remote CNS damage, while 31 children (19 boys and 12 girls) with bronchial asthma without neurological symptoms were included in the comparison group. Along with the collection of anamnestic data and clinical examination, an analysis was conducted on the influence of perinatal CNS damage on the physical development of children with bronchial asthma. For assessing physical development, a combination of Rohrer, Pinneau, Brugsch, and Vervek indices, as well as body mass index (BMI), was used.

Results: An analysis of the condition of newborns after birth revealed that 93.5% of children in the comparison group received an Apgar score of 8-10 in the first minute after birth, while in the main group, all children were born in a state of asphyxia. It was found that the age between 3 months and 6 months is particularly vulnerable for the continuation of exclusive breastfeeding and the transition to artificial feeding, which is one of the triggering mechanisms for the realization of predisposition to allergic diseases. In assessing the BMI of children with bronchial asthma against the background

of the long-term effects of perinatal CNS lesions, nearly one-third of patients (37.5%) were found to have mild or moderate nutritional disorders, with parameters ranging from -3SD to (-1SD). The comparison of the obtained anthropometric characteristics based on calculated indices showed a significant predominance of disharmonious physical development in children in the main group compared to those in the comparison group.

Conclusions: An analysis of the condition of newborns after birth established that the majority of children in the main group were born in mild (52.8%), moderate (27.8%), and severe (19.4%) asphyxia, while only 6.5% of children in the comparison group were born with mild asphyxia, and the remaining 93.5% were born with an Apgar score of 8-10. Furthermore, children with bronchial asthma, against the background of the long-term effects of perinatal CNS lesions, most commonly exhibited mild to moderate nutritional disorders with disharmonious physical development, while every third child in the comparison group was characterized by excess weight.

Keywords: bronchial asthma, perinatal lesion, central nervous system, asphyxia, body mass index, physical development, children, calculated indices.

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MARKAZIY ASAB TIZIMI PERINATAL SHIKASTLANISHINING UZOQ MUDDATLI OQIBATLARI FONIDA BRONXIAL ASTMA BILAN OG'RIGAN BOLALARNING JISMONIY RIVOJLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Tadqiqotning maqsadi: Markaziy asab tizimi perinatal shikastlanishi oqibatlarining bronxial astma bilan og'rigan bolalarning jismoniy rivojlanish ko'rsatkichlariga ta'sirini o'rganish.

Materiallar va usullar: ishning birinchi bosqichida markaziy asab tizimining perinatal shikastlanishi oqibatlari bo'lgan bolalarda bronxial astma kursining anamnestik va klinik -funktsional xususiyatlari o'rganildi. Maqolaning tahliliy qismida bronxial astma tashxisi qo'yilgan 5 yoshdan 7 yoshgacha bo'lgan 103 bolani har tomonlama tekshirish natijalari keltirilgan. Asosiy guruhni bronxial astma bilan og'rigan 72 bola (51 o'g'il va 21 qiz) tashkil etdi, ular markaziy asab tizimiga uzoq muddatli shikastlanish belgilarini ko'rsatdilar va nevrologik alomatlari bo'lmagan bronxial astma bilan kasallangan 31 bola (19 o'g'il va 12 qiz) taqqoslash guruhiga kirdi. Anamnestik ma'lumotlarni to'plash va klinik tekshiruv bilan bir qatorda, markaziy asab tizimining perinatal shikastlanishining bronxial astma bilan og'rigan bolalarning jismoniy rivojlanishiga ta'siri tahlil qilindi. Jismoniy rivojlanishni baholashda Rorer, Pin'ye, Brugsh va Vervekning hisoblash indeksleri, shuningdek, tana massasi indeksi kombinatsiyasidan foydalanildi.

Natijalar: yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarning tug'ilgandan keyingi holatini tahlil qilganda, taqqoslash guruhidagi bolalarning 93,5 foizi tug'ilgandan keyingi birinchi daqiqada 8-10 ball olgan, asosiy guruhda esa barcha bolalar asfiksiya holatida tug'ilgan. Ma'lum bo'lishicha, 3 oydan 6 oygacha bo'lgan yosh faqat emizishni davom ettirish va bolalarni sun'iy oziqlantirishga o'tkazish uchun juda zaif davrdir, bu allergik kasallikka moyillikni yuzaga chiqarishning asosiy mexanizmlaridan biridir. Bronxial astma bilan og'rigan bolalarda markaziy asab tizimining perinatal shikastlanishi oqibatlari fonida tana massasi indeksini baholashda bemorlarning deyarli uchdan birida-3CO(-1CO) parametrlari bilan yengil va o'rtacha ovqatlanish buzilishi (37,5%) aniqlandi. Olingan antropometrik xususiyatlarni hisoblash indeksleri bo'yicha taqqoslash, taqqoslash guruhidagi bolalardan farqli

o'laroq, disgarmonik jismoniy rivojlanishning asosiy guruhidagi bolalar orasida ishonchli ustunligini ko'rsatdi.

Xulosa: yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarning tug'ilgandan keyingi holatini tahlil qilishda asosiy guruhdagi bolalarning aksariyati yengil (52,8%), o'rtacha (27,8%) va og'ir (19,4%) asfiksiyada tug'ilganligi aniqlandi, taqqoslash guruhidagi bolalarning atigi 6,5% yengil asfiksiyada tug'ilgan, qolgan 93,5% esa 8-10 ballar bilan tug'ilgan. Shu bilan birga, bronxial astma bilan og'rigan bolalarda, markaziy asab tizimining perinatal shikastlanishi oqibatlarini fonida, jismoniy rivojlanishning nomutanosibliigi bilan yengil va o'rtacha ovqatlanish buzilishi eng ko'p qayd etildi, ayni paytda taqqoslash guruhining har uchinchi bolasi uchun ortiqcha vazn xarakterlidir.

Kalit so'zlar: bronxial astma, perinatal shikastlanish, markaziy asab tizimi, asfiksiya, tana massa indeksi, jismoniy rivojlanish, bolalar, hisoblash indeksleri

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ДЕТЕЙ С БРОНХИАЛЬНОЙ АСТМОЙ НА ФОНЕ ОТДАЛЕННЫХ ПОСЛЕДСТВИЯ ПЕРИНАТАЛЬНОГО ПОРАЖЕНИЯ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ НЕРВНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Цель исследования: Изучить влияние последствий перинатального поражения ЦНС на показатели физического развития детей, страдающих бронхиальной астмой.

Материалы и методы: на первом этапе работе проведено изучение анамнестических и клинико-функциональных особенностей течения бронхиальной астмы у детей с последствиями перинатального поражения центральной нервной системы. Аналитическая часть статьи содержит результаты комплексного обследования 103 детей в возрасте от 5 до 7 лет с диагнозом бронхиальная астма. Основную группу составили 72 ребенка (51 мальчик и 21 девочка) с бронхиальной астмой, имеющих признаки отдаленного поражения центральной нервной системы, а 31 ребенок (19 мальчиков и 12 девочек) больных бронхиальной астмой, не имеющих неврологической симптоматики, - вошли в группу сравнения. Наряду со сбором анамнестических данных и клинического обследования, проведен анализ влияния перинатального повреждения центральной нервной системы на физическое развитие детей, страдающих бронхиальной астмой. При оценке физического развития использована комбинация расчётных индексов Рорера, Пинье, Бругша и Вервека, а также индекс массы тела.

Результаты: При анализе состояния новорожденных детей после рождения установлено, что 93,5% детей группы сравнения на первой минуте после рождения получили оценку 8-10 баллов, тогда как в основной группе все дети были рождены в состоянии асфиксии. Оказалось, что возраст от 3-х месяцев до 6-ти является особо уязвимым для продолжения исключительно грудного вскармливания и перевода детей на искусственное вскармливание, являющееся одним из пусковых механизмов при реализации предрасположенности к аллергическому заболеванию. При оценке индекса массы тела у детей с бронхиальной астмой на фоне последствий перинатального поражения центральной нервной системы почти у трети пациентов выявлены легкое или умеренное нарушение питания (37,5%) с параметрами $-3CO$ - ($-1CO$). Сопоставление полученных антропометрических характеристик по расчетным индексам показало достоверное преобладание среди детей в основной группе дисгармоничного физического развития в отличие от детей группы сравнения.

Выводы: При анализе состояния новорожденных детей после рождения было установлено, что большинство детей основной группы родились в асфиксии легкой (52,8%), среднетяжелой (27,8%) и тяжелой степени (19,4%), тогда как лишь 6,5% детей группы сравнения родились в легкой асфиксии, а остальные 93,5% родились с оценкой 8-10 баллов. При этом у детей с бронхиальной астмой на фоне последствий перинатального поражения центральной нервной системы наиболее часто отмечаются легкие и умеренные нарушения питания с дисгармонией физического развития, тогда как для каждого третьего ребенка группы сравнения был характерен излишний вес.

Ключевые слова: бронхиальная астма, перинатальное поражение, центральная нервная система, асфиксия, индекс массы тела, физическое развитие, дети, расчетные индексы

Bronxial astma (BA) bugungi kunga kelib, tashxis qo'yish, davolash va oldini olishda erishilgan katta yutuqlarga qaramay, hali ham juda keng tarqalgan xastalik bo'lib, barqaror o'sishda davom etmoqda va shuning uchun juda dolzarb kasallik hisoblanadi [1,4,5,15]. Ma'lumki, bolalarning jismoniy rivojlanish holati (JR), bolaning sog'lig'ining yetakchi ko'rsatkichlaridan biri sifatida har doim tadqiqotchilarning diqqat markazida bo'lgan va BA holatida bu nafaqat kasallik shakllanishining bashoratchisi, balki og'ir kechishi uchun xavf omili, shuningdek terapiya samaradorligi mezoni bo'lishi mumkin [14].

Ushbu adabiy manbalar BA bilan kasallangan bolalarning JR nafaqat o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga, balki qarama-qarshi xarakterga ham ega ekanligini ko'rsatadi. Xususan, agar ba'zi mualliflar sog'lom bolalar guruhiga nisbatan BA bilan og'rigan bolalarda rivojlanish darajasi yuqori ekanligini tasdiqlasa [17,18], boshqalari esa, aksincha, BA bilan og'rigan bolalar sog'lom bolalarga qaraganda pastroq o'sish tendentsiyasiga ega ekanligini va bu tendentsiya jinsga xosligini ko'rsatadi [11].

BA va unga hamroh bo'lgan semirish o'rtasida ko'plab patogenetik aloqalar mavjudligini ko'rsatadigan bir qator ilmiy nashrlar mavjud [3]. BA bilan og'rigan bolalarda ko'pincha tana massasi indeksi (TMI) [6,8] yuqori ekanligi aniqlangan va BAning geterogen tabiatini hisobga olgan holda, semizlik bilan BA fenotipi hozirda keng muhokama qilinmoqda. Shu bilan birga, [19] shunday ilmiy tadqiqot asarlari ham mavjudki, ularda massa-bo'y indeksi sog'lom bolalar bilan taqqoslaganda nafaqat yuqori, balki past ekanligini ko'rsatadi. G. Y. Poretskova va boshqalar (2018) 6-8 yoshdagi BA bilan kasallangan o'g'il bolalar tana vaznining past parametrlari tufayli sog'lom bolalarga nisbatan TMI sezilarli darajada past bo'lganligini aniqladilar, ammo katta yoshdagi bolalar TMI oshishi bilan ajralib turadi. O'z navbatida, W. Umlawska et al. (2013) bolalarda TMI va BA o'rtasida umuman sezilarli bog'liqlik yo'qligini da'vo qilmoqda.

Zamonaviy adabiyotlarda markaziy asab tizimining (MNS) perinatal gipoksik shikastlanishining BA va boshqa allergik kasalliklarning shakllanishidagi muhim roli masalasi keng muhokama qilinadi [13]. Ko'plab ilmiy tadqiqotlar ma'lumotlari shuni ko'rsatadiki, asab tizimining perinatal patologiyasini boshdan kechirgan bolalarda bronxial astma og'irroq va tez-tez bronxo-obstruktiv sindrom, an'anaviy terapiyaning past samaradorligi va tez-tez takrorlanish bilan kechadi. Yuqoridagilarni tasdiqlashda tadqiqot mualliflari ushbu bemorlar guruhida [7,10,16] hayot uchun xavfli bo'lgan og'ir obstruktsiya hurujlarining rivojlanishini ko'rsatadigan misollar keltiradilar.

Markaziy asab tizimining perinatal shikastlanishi bo'lgan bolalarda bronxial astma markaziy asab tizimining perinatal shikastlanishi bo'lmagan bolalarga qaraganda ma'lum xususiyatlarga ega ekanligini isbotlovchi ishlar paydo bo'ldi. Shunday qilib, kasallik erta bolalikdan boshlanadi, tez-tez hurujlar va uzoq muddatli qo'zg'alishlar doimiy kursga ega, bu esa ushbu bolalarni davolashda, umumiy qabul qilingan asosiy yallig'lanishga qarshi terapiya bilan bir qatorda, markaziy asab tizimining faoliyatini yaxshilaydigan dorilarni tayinlashni talab qiladi [2,12].

Yuqoridagilarni hisobga olgan holda, BA bilan kasallangan bolalarning JR xususiyatlarini ko'rsatadigan yetarli ma'lumotlar mavjudligiga qaramay, ushbu turdagi tadqiqotlarning dolzarbligi o'z ahamiyatini saqlab qoladi. Shuni alohida ta'kidlash kerakki, hozirgi vaqtda markaziy asab tizimining perinatal patologiyasini boshdan kechirgan bolalarda bronxial astma kursining xususiyatlarini o'rganish dolzarbdir. Bronxial astma bilan og'rigan va markaziy asab tizimining perinatal

shikastlanishining uzoq muddatli oqibatlari bo'lgan bolalarning jismoniy rivojlanish ko'rsatkichlarini baholash muammosi ham kam o'rganilgan.

Ishning maqsadi: Markaziy asab tizimi perinatal shikastlanishi oqibatlarining bronxial astma bilan og'rigan bolalarning jismoniy rivojlanish ko'rsatkichlariga ta'sirini o'rganish.

Materiallar va tadqiqot usullari. Qo'yilgan maqsad asosida markaziy asab tizimi perinatal shikastlanishining bronxial astma bilan og'rigan bolalarning jismoniy rivojlanishiga ta'siri tahlil qilindi. Tadqiqot Samarqand shahridagi VBKTTMning pulmonologiya bo'limi negizida o'tkazildi. Tadqiqot 5-7 yoshdagi BA bilan kasallangan 103 bolani har tomonlama tekshirish ma'lumotlariga asoslangan. Tekshirilayotgan guruhlariga 5 yoshdan kichik va 7 yoshdan katta bolalar, shuningdek, qo'pol somatik patologiyaga, shuningdek markaziy asab tizimining organik shikastlanishiga ega bo'lganlar kiritilmagan. Anamnestik ma'lumotlarga alohida ahamiyat berildi: ayollarning sog'lig'i, homiladorlik va tug'ruq jarayoni, bolalarda esa perinatal va neonatal davrlar. Bunday e'tibor bolalarda markaziy asab tizimining perinatal shikastlanishi oqibatlarini rivojlanish sabablarini aniqlash bilan bog'liq edi. Tekshiruv guruhiga faqat o'z vaqtida tug'ilgan va yengil markaziy asab tizimiga zarar yetish belgilari bo'lgan bolalar kirdi. Anamnestik ma'lumotlar tug'ruqxonalarining almashinuv kartalari va bolalarning rivojlanish kartalari ma'lumotlariga asoslangan. O'rta darajadagi bronxial astma bilan og'rigan barcha bolalar (n=103) markaziy asab tizimining perinatal shikastlanishining oqibatlari mavjudligini aniqlash uchun klinik va nevrologik tekshiruvdan o'tkazildi. Ma'lum bo'lishicha, BA bilan og'rigan 72 bolada (51 o'g'il va 21 qiz) markaziy asab tizimining shikastlanish belgilari bo'lgan bu bolalarni asosiy guruhga kiritish uchun asos bo'lgan, 31 bolada (19 o'g'il va 12 qiz) BA bilan og'rigan bemorlarda perinatal markaziy asab tizimining shikastlanishining uzoq muddatli oqibatlari belgilari topilmagan va ular taqqoslashlar guruhga kiritilgan.

Natijalar va ularni muhokama qilish. Yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarning tug'ilgandan keyin holatini tahlil qilganda, taqqoslash guruhidagi bolalarning aksariyati (93,5%) tug'ilgandan keyingi birinchi daqiqada 8-10 ball olgan, asosiy guruhda esa barcha bolalar asfiksiya holatida tug'ilgan (1-rasm).

1-rasm. Tekshirilgan bolalar tug'ilgandan keyingi 1-daqiqada Apgar shkalasi bo'yicha baholash

Yengil asfiksiyaga mos keladigan Apgar shkalasi 6-7 ball asosiy bolalarning 52,8% (n=38) va taqqoslash guruhidagi bolalarning 6,5% (n=2) tomonidan kuzatilgan. Shuningdek, asosiy guruhdagi bolalarning 27,8 %i (n=20) o'rtacha darajadagi asfiksiya holatida (Apgar shkalasi ballari 4-5 ball) va 19,4 % (n=14) og'ir darajadagi asfiksiya holatida tug'ilgan.

Tug'ilgandan keyingi 5-daqiqada asosiy guruhidagi yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarning holatini baholashda Apgar shkalasi bo'yicha 8-10 ball olgan bolalar soni 6,9% gacha (n=5) ko'payganligi aniqlandi, yengil asfiksiya 55,6% (n=40) da aniqlandi, o'rtacha va og'ir asfiksiya esa tashxis qo'yilgan yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarning uchdan biridan ko'prog'ida, mos ravishda 23,6% (n=17) va 13,9% (n=10) holatlar mavjud (2-rasm).

Ma'lumki, allergiya paydo bo'lishi uchun bolalarning ovqatlanishi muhim rol o'ynaydi-bolalar sun'iy oziqlantirishga qanchalik tez o'tkazilsa, allergiya xavfi shunchalik yuqori bo'ladi. Shu munosabat bilan biz tekshirgan bolalarda emizish davomiyligini tahlil qilishga qaror qildik. Ma'lum bo'lishicha, ko'krak suti 0 oydan 36 oygacha bo'lgan bolalar tomonidan qabul qilingan, o'rtacha $12,2 \pm 0,97$ oy (1-jadval). Afsuski, tekshirilgan bolalar orasida, ham asosiy, ham taqqoslash guruhida, bir oylik yoshga to'lmagan bolalar (19,4%) sutli aralashmalarni olishgan.

1 oydan 3 oygacha bo'lgan taqqoslash guruhidan ko'ra ko'proq asosiy guruh bolalari tomonidan ona suti qabul qilingan (mos ravishda 33,3% va 25,8%). Holbuki, 3 oydan 6 oygacha bo'lgan davrda asosiy guruhda ona sutini emadigan bolalar taqqoslash guruhiga qaraganda ikki baravar kam edi (11,1%, taqqoslash guruhida 22,6%). 6 oydan katta bo'lgan ona sutini emadigan bolalar soni bo'yicha tekshirilgan guruhlarda statistik jihatdan sezilarli farq aniqlanmagan (asosiy guruhda 36,1% va taqqoslash guruhida 32,3%). Olingan ma'lumotlarga asoslanib, bu faqat emizishni davom ettirish va bolalarni sun'iy oziqlantirishga o'tkazish uchun o'ta sezgir bo'lgan 3 oydan 6 oygacha bo'lgan davr deb taxmin qilish mumkin, bu allergik kasallikka moyillikni amalga oshirishda qo'zg'atuvchilardan biri bo'lishi mumkin.

1-jadval

Tekshirilgan bolalarda emizish davomiyligi

Emizish davomiyligi	Asosiy guruh, n=72		Taqqoslash guruhi, n=31		Jami, n=103	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
1 oydan kam	14	19,4	6	19,4	20	19,4
1 oydan 3 oygacha	24	33,3	8	25,8	32	31,1
3 oydan 6 oygacha	8	11,1	7	22,6	15	14,6
6 oydan ortiq	26	36,1	10	32,3	36	34,9

Tana massa indeksini (TMI) baholash shuni ko'rsatdiki, asosiy va taqqoslash guruhida bolalarning mos ravishda 33,3% va 58,1% (asosiy guruhga qaraganda 1,7 baravar ko'p) TMI ko'rsatkichlari 1CO-(+1CO) medianasiga mos keladi, ya'ni ushbu ko'rsatkichlar me'yoriy qiymatlar doirasida edi (2-jadval). Markaziy asab tizimining perinatal shikastlanishi oqibatlarini fonida BA bilan og'rigan bolalarda TMI ko'rsatkichlari eng ko'p (37,5%) 3CO-(-1CO) medianada joylashgan, bu yengil yoki o'rtacha ovqatlanish buzilishini ko'rsatdi, taqqoslash guruhida esa faqat 1 bola (3,2%) TMI -2CO-(1CO) medianaga to'g'ri keldi. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, taqqoslash guruhidagi bemorlar har uchinchi bolada uchraydigan ortiqcha vazn (38,7%) bilan ajralib turardi.

2-jadval

Tekshirilgan bolalarda TMI ko'rsatkichlari

Guruhlar	-3CO-(-1CO)		-1CO-(+1CO)		+1CO-(+2CO)	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Jami bolalar (n=103)	28	27,2	42	40,8	33	32,0
Asosiy guruh (n=72)	27	37,5*	24	33,3	21	29,2
Taqqoslash guruhi (n=31)	1	3,2	18	58,1	12	38,7*

Izoh: guruh ko'rsatkichlariga nisbatan qiymatlarning ishonchliligi-1CO-(+1 CO) (*- p<0,01)

BA bilan og'rigan bolalarning jismoniy rivojlanishini har tomonlama baholash uchun Rorer, Pin'ye, Brugsh va Vervek hisoblash indekslarining kombinatsiyasi ishlatilgan. Olingan antropometrik xususiyatlarni taqqoslash taqqoslash, guruhidagi bolalardan farqli o'laroq, disgarmonik jismoniy rivojlanish asosiy guruhda BA bilan kasallangan bolalar orasida ishonchli ustunlikni ko'rsatdi. Shunday qilib, asosiy guruhda tana o'lchamlarining nisbati – bo'ylama ko'ndalangga nisbatan - 52,8% hollarda bo'y o'sishining o'rtacha yoki aniq ustunligi, ya'ni Vervek indeksining qiymatlari 1,25 birlikdan yuqori bo'lgan o'rtacha yoki aniq dolixomorfiya aniqlandi. Markaziy asab tizimining perinatal shikastlanishining uzoq muddatli oqibatlarini bo'lgan BA bilan kasallangan bolalarning 38,9 foizida Rorer indeksining qiymati 10,7 kg/m³ dan kam bo'lib, bu jismoniy rivojlanishning pastligini ko'rsatdi (3-jadval).

3-jadval

BA bilan kasallangan bolalarning jismoniy rivojlanishini indeksli baholash ko'rsatkichlari

Indekslar		Asosiy guruh (n=72)		Taqqoslash guruhi (n=31)		Jami (n=103)	
		n	%	n	%	n	%
Rorer	kam rivojlanish	28	38,9*	2	6,5	30	29,1
	garmonik	40	55,6	11	35,5	51	49,5
	yuqori	4	5,5*	18	58,0	22	21,4
Pin'ye	past	10	13,9*	-	-	10	9,7
	o'rtacha darajadan past	15	20,8*	3	9,7	18	17,5
	o'rtacha	42	58,3	11	35,5	53	51,4
	o'rtacha darajadan yuqori, normal	5	6,9*	17	54,8	22	21,4

Brugsh	tor ko'krak	25	34,7*	2	6,5	27	26,2
	normal ko'krak qafasi	35	48,6	13	41,9	48	46,6
	keng ko'krak	12	16,7*	16	51,6	28	27,2
Vervek	aniq braximorfiya	5	6,9	3	9,7	8	7,8
	o'rtacha braximorfiya	6	8,3	3	9,7	9	8,7
	mezomorf tip	24	33,4	19	61,2	43	41,7
	o'rtacha dolixomorfiya	22	30,6*	3	9,7	25	24,3
	ifodalangan dolixomorfiya	15	20,8*	3	9,7	18	17,5

Izoh: * - taqqoslash guruhiga nisbatan ma'lumotlarning ishonchliligi ($p < 0,05-0,001$)

Pin'ye indeksidagi parametrlarni o'rganish va qiyosiy baholash asosiy guruhdagi bolalarda jismoniy rivojlanishning – 34,7%, taqqoslash guruhidagi bolalarga qaraganda – 9,7% sezilarli darajada past ko'rsatkichlarini aniqladi. Asosiy guruhdagi BA bilan og'rigan bolalarda Brugsh indeksi bo'yicha hisoblangan tekshirilgan bolalarning xususiyatlari ko'pincha tor ko'krak va nomutanosib tana tuzilishini ko'rsatdi: bolalarning 34,7 foizida indeksning qiymati standart yosh ko'rsatkichlaridan past edi. Umuman olganda, asosiy guruhdagi bolalarning atigi 33,4 foizi va taqqoslash guruhidagi 35,5 foizi uyg'un jismoniy rivojlanishga ega edi, asosiy guruhdagi nomutanosiblik ko'pincha holatlarning yarmidan ko'pida past jismoniy rivojlanish (JR) bilan bog'liq edi, taqqoslash guruhida esa jismoniy rivojlanish o'rtacha darajadan yuqori edi (4-jadval).

4-jadval

Tekshirilgan bolalarning jismoniy rivojlanishining uyg'unligini baholash

Guruhlar	Garmonik JR		Disgarmonik JR		Keskin disgarmonik JR	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Jami bolalar (n=103)	35	34,0	42	40,8	26	25,2
Asosiy guruh (n=72)	24	33,4	28	38,8	20	27,8
Taqqoslash guruhi (n=31)	11	35,5	14	45,2	6	19,3

Xulosalar:

1. Yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarning tug'ilgandan keyingi holatini tahlil qilganda, markaziy asab tizimining perinatal shikastlanishi ta'siriga ega bo'lgan BA bilan kasallangan bolalarning aksariyati yengil (52,8%), o'rtacha (27,8%) va og'ir (19,4%) asfiksiyada tug'ilganligi aniqlandi, nevrologik alomatlari bo'lmagan BA bilan kasallangan bolalarning atigi 6,5% yengil asfiksiya va qolgan 93,5% 8-10 ball bilan tug'ilgan.

2. Markaziy asab tizimining perinatal shikastlanishi oqibatlarini fonida BA bilan og'rigan bolalarda yengil va o'rtacha ovqatlanish buzilishi ko'pincha qayd etiladi. Shu bilan birga, taqqoslash guruhining har uchinchi farzandi ortiqcha vaznga ega edi.

3. Rorer, Pin'ye, Brugsh va Vervek hisoblangan indeksleri kombinatsiyasidan foydalangan holda BA bilan kasallangan bolalarning jismoniy rivojlanishini har tomonlama baholash taqqoslash guruhidagi bolalardan farqli o'laroq, disgarmonik jismoniy rivojlanish markaziy asab tizimining perinatal shikastlanishi oqibatlarini bo'lgan BA bilan kasallangan bolalar orasida ishonchli ustunlikni ko'rsatdi.

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